

ANALYSIS ON COMPOSITE LAMINATES BY A NEW CONFORMING PLATE BENDING ELEMENT

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ABSTRACT

A multilayered anisotropic flat plate element which includes the effects of the transverse shear deformation is developed by use of displacement formulation. The proposed rectangular plate element has eight degrees-of-freedom (DOF) at each nodal point, u^0 , v^0 , w^0 , $\partial w^0 / \partial x$, $\partial w^0 / \partial y$, $\partial^2 w^0 / \partial x \partial y$, γ_x , γ_y , given a total of 32 DOF. The element formulation is based on Reddy's higher-order theory which satisfies the zero transverse shear stress boundary conditions on the top and bottom faces of the plate and requires no shear correction coefficients. In order to demonstrate the accuracy of the developed finite element, the numerical results compared with the available closed-form solutions, the 3-D linear elasticity theory results, and the other numerical results are given. The tests carried out show that the element is a simple and reliable 32 DOF thin or thick multilayer laminated plate element.

Keywords : multilayer laminated plate, conforming element, higher-order finite element model.

1. INTRODUCTION

Laminate composite plates find wide applications in aeronautical and aerospace industries as well as in other fields of modern engineering technology. The increased use of fiber-reinforced composite plates is primarily due to their high stiffness-to-weight ratio and due to their anisotropic material property that can be tailored through variation of the fiber orientation and stacking sequence.

Exact three-dimensional analysis¹⁻³ have indicated that, for laminate composite plates, the distortion of the deformed normal due to transverse shear is dependent, not only on the laminate thickness, but also on the orientation and degree of orthotropy of the individual layers. Therefore the Kirchhoff-Love assumption, that normals to the middle surface before deformation remain straight and normal to it after deformation, is not adequate for the analysis of moderately thick laminates. From the above, it is evident that any approximate

effective bidimensional theory for multilayered anisotropic plates should account for the effects of transverse shear deformations. To improve the situation, various refined plate theories have been developed. These include first-order shear deformation theories⁴⁻⁶, higher-order shear deformation theories⁷⁻¹⁰, and first-order zig-zag theories^{11,12}. Excellent review papers on these two-dimensional shear deformation theories can be found^{13,14}.

Because of the complexity of the theories involved, the investigations discussed above are severely limited in their applications. On the other hand, the finite element method provides a convenient and powerful technique for analyzing complex structures. There has been considerable effort of late directed toward the development of shear deformable, multilayered anisotropic plate finite elements¹⁵⁻¹⁸. As a basis for the development of a displacement plate element of this type, the previous authors have employed the first-order shear deformation plate theory developed by Yang *et al.*⁴⁻⁶. These elements provide good results for the global response of the plate; that is, for deflections, natural frequencies, and buckling loads. However, a more sophisticated element would be required for studying the through-the-thickness stress response in regions of discontinuities such as boundaries.

A higher-order finite element model was developed by Phan and Reddy¹⁹. The theory used in this finite element formulation is presented in Refs. 9 and 20. The transverse displacement of the plate element is interpolated through a cubic displacement function while the in-plane displacements and rotations are interpolated linearly. The element contains a total 7 DOF per node. An important characteristic of this higher-order formulation is that through-the-thickness transverse shear stress distribution is parabolic and the element appears to be free from shear locking. On the other hand, in the first-order theory transverse shear stresses are assumed to vary linearly through the thickness, and therefore shear-correction factors had to be used to account for the actual parabolic distribution.

Finite elements based on Reddy's^{9,20} higher-order shear deformation theory also were derived by Ren and Hinton²¹. These authors slightly modified the degrees of freedom used by Phan and Reddy. The element by Ren and Hinton was found to be flexible compared to that of Phan and Reddy²² and gave results approaching towards the exact solution. It was felt that the reason for this improvement may be due to the use of the transverse shear-strain components as degrees of freedom.

The conventional variational formulation of the classical plate theory as well as the higher order theory involves second order derivatives of the transverse displacement. Such a variational form requires that the element displacement functions be C^1 continuous, i.e., in the finite element modelling of such theory one should impose the continuity of not only the transverse displacement but also its derivatives along the inter-element boundary. To overcome these requirements on the continuity of the displacement functions, a rectangular finite element using mixed principles was developed by Putcha and Reddy²³. The element has eleven DOF (three displacements, two rotations, and six moment results) per node. The element was proved to be quite accurate for stability and vibration analysis.

Chomkwah and Avula²⁴, in a recent study, performed a high-order theory for laminated composite plates using the Lagrange multiplier technique which involved z^2 terms in the displacement field. Although the theory provides good results for the response of the plate, the storage requirements due to large number of variables and computer costs make it inconvenient.

The purpose of this article is to develop, on the basis of higher-order theory proposed by Reddy^{9,20}, a rectangular flat finite element which includes the distortion of the deformed normal to the reference surface, the transverse shear effects, as well as the coupling effects of stretching and bending. The transverse displacement of the present element is interpolated through a bicubic displacement function while the in-plane displacements and shear-rotations are interpolated linearly. These functions satisfy the inter-element compatibil-

ity and the constant strain conditions. The nodal parameters consist of the three generalized displacements u^0 , v^0 , and w^0 ; the two shear rotations γ_x and γ_y ; the two total rotations $\partial w^0/\partial x$, and $\partial w^0/\partial y$, and the mixed second derivative $\partial^2 w^0/\partial x \partial y$. The numerical results are compared with the available closed-form solutions, the 3-D linear elasticity theory results, and the other numerical results.

2. BASIC EQUATIONS

Consider a plate of constant thickness h composed of layers with different orientations. The origin of the coordinate system is located at the midplane with the z -axis normal to the midplane. The material of each layer is assumed to possess a plane of elastic symmetry parallel to the xy -plane. The midplane is denoted by Ω .

The higher-order theory is based on the following assumed displacement field^{9,20} :

$$\begin{aligned} u &= u^0 + z \left[\psi_x - 4/3 (z/h)^2 (\psi_x + \partial w/\partial x) \right], \\ v &= v^0 + z \left[\psi_y - 4/3 (z/h)^2 (\psi_y + \partial w/\partial y) \right], \\ w &= w^0, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where u , v , and w are the displacement components in the x , y , and z -directions, respectively; u^0 , v^0 denote the displacements of a point (x, y) on the midplane, and ψ_x and ψ_y are the rotations of normals to the midplane about the y and x -axes, respectively.

In this paper, we define new variables γ_x and γ_y as

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_x &= \psi_x + \partial w/\partial x \\ \gamma_y &= \psi_y + \partial w/\partial y \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The displacement components in Equations 1 thus become

$$\begin{aligned} u &= u^0 + z[\gamma_x - \partial w/\partial x - 4/3(z/h)^2 \gamma_x] \\ v &= v^0 + z[\gamma_y - \partial w/\partial y - 4/3(z/h)^2 \gamma_y] \\ w &= w^0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Note that γ_x and γ_y are the shear-strain components in the transverse direction.

The strains associated with the displacement field in Equations 3 are

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_1 &= \epsilon_1^0 + z(\kappa_1^0 + z^2 \kappa_1^2), & \epsilon_4 &= \epsilon_4^0 + z^2 \kappa_4^2, \\ \epsilon_2 &= \epsilon_2^0 + z(\kappa_2^0 + z^2 \kappa_2^2), & \epsilon_5 &= \epsilon_5^0 + z^2 \kappa_5^2, \\ \epsilon_3 &= 0, & \epsilon_6 &= \epsilon_6^0 + z(\kappa_6^0 + z^2 \kappa_6^2), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_1^0 &= \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x}, & \kappa_1^0 &= \frac{\partial \gamma_x}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2}, & \kappa_1^2 &= -\frac{4}{3h^2} \frac{\partial \gamma_x}{\partial x}, \\ \epsilon_2^0 &= \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y}, & \kappa_2^0 &= \frac{\partial \gamma_y}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2}, & \kappa_2^2 &= -\frac{4}{3h^2} \frac{\partial \gamma_y}{\partial y}, \\ \epsilon_4^0 &= \gamma_y, & \kappa_4^2 &= -\frac{4}{h^2} \gamma_y, \\ \epsilon_5^0 &= \gamma_x, & \kappa_5^2 &= -\frac{4}{h^2} \gamma_x, \\ \epsilon_6^0 &= \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x}, & \kappa_6^0 &= \frac{\partial \gamma_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \gamma_y}{\partial x} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y}, \\ \kappa_6^2 &= -\frac{4}{3h^2} \left(\frac{\partial \gamma_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \gamma_y}{\partial x} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Owing to the existence of a plane of elastic symmetry, the constitutive relation for the k th layer in the (x, y) system are given by

$$\sigma_i^{(k)} = Q_{ij}^{(k)} \epsilon_j^{(k)} \quad i, j = 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, \quad (6)$$

where Q_{ij} are the plane-stress reduced stiffness components of the layered material after being transformed to the global coordinate system.

Using Equations 4 and 6 the strain energy can be expressed in terms of a set of generalized displacements

$$\begin{aligned} U &= U_b + U_s, \\ U_b &= \int_{A^e} [\{\epsilon_0\}^T [A] \{\epsilon_0\} + \{\epsilon_0\}^T [B] \{\kappa_1\} + \{\epsilon_0\}^T [E] \{\kappa_2\} \\ &\quad + \{\kappa_1\}^T [B] \{\epsilon_0\} + \{\kappa_1\}^T [D] \{\kappa_1\} + \{\kappa_1\}^T [F] \{\kappa_2\} \\ &\quad + \{\kappa_2\}^T [E] \{\epsilon_0\} + \{\kappa_2\}^T [F] \{\kappa_1\} + \{\kappa_2\}^T [H] \{\kappa_2\}] d\Omega^e, \\ U_s &= \int_{A^e} \{R_0\}^T [G] \{R_0\} d\Omega^e, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \{\epsilon_0\}^T &= \{\epsilon_1^0 \ \epsilon_2^0 \ \epsilon_6^0\}, & \{\kappa_1\}^T &= \{\kappa_1^0 \ \kappa_2^0 \ \kappa_6^0\}, \\ \{\kappa_2\}^T &= \{\kappa_1^2 \ \kappa_2^2 \ \kappa_6^2\}, & \{R_0\}^T &= \{\epsilon_4^0 \ \epsilon_5^0 \ \kappa_4^2 \ \kappa_5^2\}, \\ (A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij}, E_{ij}, F_{ij}, H_{ij}) &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} Q_{ij}^{(k)}(1, z, z^2, z^3, z^4, z^6) dz \quad i, j = 1, 2, 6, \\ (A_{ij}, D_{ij}, F_{ij}) &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} Q_{ij}^{(k)}(1, z^2, z^4) dz \quad i, j = 4, 5, \\ [G] &= \begin{bmatrix} A_{44} & A_{45} & D_{44} & D_{45} \\ & A_{55} & D_{45} & D_{55} \\ & & F_{44} & F_{45} \\ \text{Sym.} & & & F_{55} \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

3. FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION

As is known, the accuracy of the finite element solution depends on the ability of the assumed interpolation functions to accurately model the deformation modes of the structure.

Since the coupling between extension, bending and transverse shear deformation states affects the static and dynamic response of the laminated anisotropic plates, a correct finite element displacement formulation should model such a coupling.

The proposed rectangular plate element has eight DOF at each nodal point, u^0 , v^0 , w^0 , $\partial w^0 / \partial x$, $\partial w^0 / \partial y$, $\partial^2 w^0 / \partial x \partial y$, γ_x , γ_y , given a total of 32 DOF. Let the domain Ω be decomposed into a set of finite elements. The arrangement of node indices is shown in Figure 1. It can be shown that over each element Ω^e , the field variables can be represented by the following expressions which satisfy the inter-element compatibility and the constant strain conditions^{25,26} (u stands for u^0 , v^0 , γ_x , and γ_y):

$$u = \sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^2 N_{0i}^{(0)}(\xi) N_{0j}^{(0)}(\eta) u_{ij} \quad (8a)$$

Figure 1. Global and local coordinate system and node indices for rectangular element.

$$\begin{aligned}
 w^0 = \sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^2 & \left[N_{0i}^{(1)}(\xi) N_{0j}^{(1)}(\eta) w_{ij}^0 + N_{1i}^{(1)}(\xi) N_{0j}^{(1)}(\eta) (\partial w^0 / \partial x)_{ij} \right. \\
 & \left. + N_{0i}^{(1)}(\xi) N_{1j}^{(1)}(\eta) (\partial w^0 / \partial y)_{ij} + N_{1i}^{(1)}(\xi) N_{1j}^{(1)}(\eta) (\partial^2 w^0 / \partial x \partial y)_{ij} \right]
 \end{aligned} \quad (8b)$$

where $(\xi = x/a_e$ and $\eta = y/b_e)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_{01}^{(0)}(\xi) &= 1 - \xi; & N_{02}^{(0)}(\xi) &= \xi; \\
 N_{01}^{(1)}(\xi) &= 1 - 3\xi^2 + 2\xi^3; & N_{02}^{(1)}(\xi) &= \xi^2(3 - 2\xi) \\
 N_{11}^{(1)}(\xi) &= a_e \xi(\xi^2 - 2\xi + 1); & N_{12}^{(1)}(\xi) &= a_e \xi^2(\xi - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

and similarly for $N_{01}^{(0)}(\eta)$, $N_{02}^{(0)}(\eta)$, etc., replacing ξ with η and a_e with b_e in above. Denote the nodal displacement vector for this four-node element as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \{\delta_e\}^T &= \{u_i^0, v_i^0, w_i^0, (\partial w^0 / \partial x)_i, (\partial w^0 / \partial y)_i, (\partial^2 w^0 / \partial x \partial y)_i, \gamma_{xi}, \gamma_{yi}\}, \\
 \text{where } u_i^0 &= \{u_1^0, u_2^0, u_3^0, u_4^0\}, \text{ etc.}
 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Therefore it is easy to obtain the strain energy for the eth element as

$$U_e = \frac{1}{2} \{\delta_e\}^T [k_e] \{\delta_e\}, \quad (10)$$

where $[k_e]$ is the stiffness matrix of order 32 by 32. External loadings and boundary conditions are subjected to the usual finite element analysis considerations.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In order to test the accuracy of the present higher-order element, the problem of simply supported square laminated plate of side length, a , under sinusoidal loading with intensity q_0 is re-examined. The material properties used are

$$E_1/E_2 = 25, \quad G_{12}/E_2 = 0.5, \quad G_{23}/E_2 = 0.2, \quad \nu_{12} = 0.25$$

It is assumed further that $G_{12} = G_{13}, \nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = \nu_{23}$.

Here, we consider a four-layer $[0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$ square cross-ply laminated plate. This example is chosen because there exists an exact three-dimensional elasticity solutions²⁷ and analysis results¹⁹. The deflections and stresses are non-dimensionalized as follows :

$$\bar{w} = \frac{w\left(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{a}{2}, 0\right) E_2 h^3}{q_0 a^4} \times 10^2, \quad \bar{\sigma}_1 = \sigma_1 \left(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{a}{2}, \frac{h}{2}\right) \frac{h^2}{q_0 a^2}, \quad \bar{\sigma}_2 = \sigma_2 \left(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{a}{2}, \frac{h}{4}\right) \frac{h^2}{q_0 a^2},$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_6 = \sigma_6 \left(0, 0, \frac{h}{2}\right) \frac{h^2}{q_0 a^2}, \quad \bar{\sigma}_5 = \sigma_5 \left(0, \frac{a}{2}, 0\right) \frac{h}{q_0 a}, \quad \bar{\sigma}_4 = \sigma_4 \left(\frac{a}{2}, 0, 0\right) \frac{h}{q_0 a}$$

Due to the existing biaxial symmetry, only one-quarter of the plate is modelled. The numerical results obtained using the present element in Table 1 are compared with the exact solutions, the closed-form solutions from Phan and Reddy¹⁹ and their finite element results. The effect of mesh on the deflections and stresses of the plate for different side-to-thickness ratios is apparent from the results. For a given thickness, the results of present element converge quite rapidly to the the closed-form solutions as the number of elements in the mesh is increased. The stresses in the finite element method are evaluated at the Gauss points. The accuracy of the present solutions are apparent from the Table 1.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

A displacement-based higher-order plate element has been presented for multilayer laminates which includes the effects of the transverse shear deformation theory. This element has been applied to the analysis of simply supported square laminate for both deflections and stresses. Predicted results have been shown to be in good agreement with the closed-form solutions. Similar accuracy should be expected if the present element is extended to the analysis of the stability and vibration of anisotropic rectangular plates.

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Table 1. The nondimensionalized deflections and stresses in a four-layer $[0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$ simply-supported square plate subjected to sinusoidal loading

a/h	Source	\bar{w}	$\bar{\sigma}_1$	$\bar{\sigma}_2$	$-\bar{\sigma}_6$	$\bar{\sigma}_4$	$\bar{\sigma}_5$
10	3 – DES ^a	0.7434	0.5990	0.4030	0.0276	0.1960	0.3010
	CFS ^b	0.7147	0.5456	0.3888	0.0268	0.1431	0.2640
	5 × 5 mesh	0.7194 ^c	0.5451	0.3876	0.0268	0.1452	0.2630
		(0.7161)	(0.5427)	(0.3855)	(0.0266)	(0.1531)	(0.2631)
	4 × 4 mesh	0.7205	0.5429	0.3861	0.0268	0.1453	0.2628
		(0.7169)	(0.5408)	(0.3833)	(0.0265)	(0.1532)	(0.2627)
20	2 × 2 mesh	0.7293	0.5217	0.3749	0.0260	0.1544	0.2583
		(0.7239)	(0.5178)	(0.3634)	(0.0252)	(0.1550)	(0.2571)
	3 – DES	0.5173	0.5430	0.3080	0.0230	0.1560	0.3280
	CFS	0.5060	0.5393	0.3043	0.0228	0.1234	0.2824
	5 × 5 mesh	0.5102	0.5371	0.3029	0.0228	0.1234	0.2821
		(0.5066)	(0.5363)	(0.3013)	(0.0226)	(0.1235)	(0.2817)
100	4 × 4 mesh	0.5106	0.5352	0.3015	0.0227	0.1234	0.2818
		(0.5068)	(0.5341)	(0.2994)	(0.0225)	(0.1236)	(0.2811)
	2 × 2 mesh	0.5048	0.5189	0.2903	0.0218	0.1237	0.2753
		(0.5040)	(0.5023)	(0.2807)	(0.0213)	(0.1237)	(0.2707)
	3 – DES	0.4385	0.5390	0.2690	0.0213	0.1380	0.3390
	CFS	0.4343	0.5387	0.2708	0.0213	0.1117	0.2897
100	5 × 5 mesh	0.4342	0.5322	0.2687	0.0212	0.1103	0.2887
		(0.4320)	(0.5301)	(0.2664)	(0.0211)	(0.1085)	(0.2851)
	4 × 4 mesh	0.4331	0.5251	0.2660	0.0210	0.1079	0.2812
		(0.4295)	(0.5231)	(0.2632)	(0.0208)	(0.1029)	(0.2797)
	2 × 2 mesh	0.3987	0.4885	0.2402	0.0856	0.0856	0.2039
		(0.3779)	(0.4320)	(0.2191)	(0.0176)	(0.0181)	(0.1774)

^a 3-DES, 3-dimensional elasticity solution²⁷

^b CFS, closed-form solutions¹⁹

^c First value is the presented finite element results and the value in parenthesis is the finite element results from Reference 19